

The values of the changes in free energy (ΔG) enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the metal ligand complex forming reaction have been calculated at 25°, 30° and 35° using the relations—

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

$$\frac{d \log K}{d(1/T)} = \frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

they are summarised in Table 2.

It is concluded that with the change in temperature there was no appreciable change in the value of stability constants or which almost remain constant.

The order of stability constants of metal complexes as given below are in good agreement with Irving-Williams order

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. K. A. Thaker, Head of the Chemistry Department for providing necessary research facilities. We are also thankful to Saurashtra University for the scholarship to Y.Z.P.

References

1. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
2. Y. Z. PATHAK and G. B. JOSHI, *J. Inst. of Chemists (India)*, 1978, 50, 116.
3. Y. Z. PATHAK and J. B. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 210.
4. J. BJERRUM "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution" P. HAASE and SONS, Copenhagen.
5. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
6. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3129.

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Ni(II) with Iminodiacetic Acid (IMDA) as Primary Ligand and Thioglycollic, Thiolactic, Thiomalic Acid and Corresponding Amino Acid as Secondary Ligands

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Manuscript received 10 October 1979, accepted 30
December 1979

BHATTACHARYA and co-workers¹⁻⁴ have investigated the mixed ligand system (MAL) involving

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bivalent metal ions like Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Histidine. Iminodiacetic acid, nitrilo tri-acetic acid as primary ligands and polyhydroxy phenols or aminoacids as secondary ligands. Various mixed ligand complexes with IMDA⁵ as the primary ligand have been studied. In the present investigation attempt have been made to study the formation constants of the title systems.

IMDA is known to form 1 : 1 complex with Ni(II) at low pH and the complex is stable at higher pH, where the combination of secondary ligand starts. The reaction can be shown as follows :

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{(MAL)}{(MA)(L)}$$

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A. R. quality. Ni(II) perchlorates was prepared from the nickel carbonate and the metal content was determined and checked. All the solutions have been prepared in conductivity water.

Metrohm E 350 A pH meter (accuracy +0.05) was used and the titrations were carried out at 30°, using constant temperature bath (accuracy = 0.1°).

The nature of the curves can be interpreted as done in earlier publications⁶. In the secondary ligand two equivalent extra acid has been added, in order to account for the extra hydrogen ions liberated due to the combination of primary ligand IMDA. n⁻ and P^L can be calculated using same equation as in earlier cases⁷. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{MA} were obtained by using the method of averages⁸; and the values are presented in Table I.

Discussion

It is observed that in case of thioacids the values of mixed ligand formation constants K_{Ni IMDA L}^{Ni IMDA} are lower than K_{Ni L}^{Ni L}. This may be due to the charge repulsion between primary ligand and secondary ligand. In case of thiomalic acid the differences between K_{Ni L}^{Ni L} and K_{Ni IMDA L}^{Ni IMDA} is more because thiomalate ion has three negative charges and has a bigger size resulting in greater electrostatic repulsion.

In case of amino acids, the order of the formation constants of the reaction MA + L is same as in the binary M + L system. This can be explained in terms of their basicities of the secondary ligands⁹⁻¹⁰. However, the values of K_{Ni A L}^{Ni A} are significantly lower than the values of K_{Ni L}^{Ni L}. This can be explained to be due to the charge repulsion between the primary

TABLE 1 - MIXED LIGAND COMPLEX FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF Ni(II) AT 30°

L	log K Ni.IMDA Ni.IMDA.L	L	log K Ni.IMDA Ni.IMDA.L
Thioglycollic acid.	5.34±0.02	Glycine	4.85±0.03*
Thiolactic acid.	5.94±0.02	α-Alanine	4.59±0.02*
Thiomalic acid.	5.91±0.01	Aspartic acid.	5.18±0.04

*Values taken from literature—Reference No. 3.

ligand and secondary ligand. The values of $\log K_{NiL}^{Ni} - \log K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA}$ where L=aspartic acid is higher because aspartic acid has two negative charges and hence the repulsion between the primary charged ligand ion and secondary ligand ion is still more.

It is observed that in the (Ni. IMDA. thio-acid) systems, the behaviour of thioacids is similar to that of the σ -bonding amino acids. The $\log K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA} - \log K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA,L}$ values are nearly same for the pairs of glycine-Thioglycollic acid, α -alanine-thiolactic acid and aspartic acid-thiomalic acid. This indicates that in both the cases the factor responsible for the lowering of the values of $K_{NiL}^{Ni,IMDA}$ is electrostatic repulsion. The situation should have been different if there would have been significant Ni→S π interaction in the thio acid complexes. Therefore, the role of Ni→S π -interaction, if present, is not very significant. The strengthening of Ni→S bond in the mercapto acid complexes is due to σ -interactions as explained by Jorgenson and Klopman¹¹⁻¹².

References

1. I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 742.
2. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1975, 75, 123.
3. J. D. JOSHI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 57.
4. J. D. JOSHI and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 344.
5. B. E. LEACH and R. J. ANGELICI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 907.
6. B. R. PANCHAL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 49, 469.
7. I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 469.
8. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 73.
9. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 881.
10. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 941.
11. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Structure & Bonding*, 1967, 3, 106.
12. G. KLOPMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 223.

Polarographic Reduction of Zn(II) and Mn(II) in the Presence of Aqueous Mixtures of Propylene Carbonate

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Manuscript received 26 September 1978, revised 21 August 1979, accepted 9 February 1980

PROPYLENE carbonate which has a fairly high dielectric constant¹ ($\epsilon_{25^\circ} = 64.92$) is a new solvent in so far as the polarography of inorganic depolarizers in organic solvents is concerned². A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of inorganic depolarizers in aqueous mixtures of this solvent still remains untouched. With this aim in view a polarographic study of the behaviour of Zn(II) and Mn(II) in aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate has been undertaken.

Experimental

ZnCl₂, MnCl₂, KCl were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. Propylene carbonate was a 'Riedel' product. All the solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of each depolarizer in the solutions was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and that of the supporting electrolyte (KCl) at 0.1 M. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL50) was used. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used to suppress the maximum of Mn(II). Since no maximum appeared in the case of Zn(II) in the present study, addition of suppressor was avoided. The temperature was kept at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M KCl, open circuit): $m = 2.34$ mg/sec, $t = 3.8$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.2010$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}, $h_{0.01} = 58.50$ cm.

The number of electrons (n) involved in the electro-reduction of Zn(II) and Mn(II) being well established (n=2), Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of 'D' at different percentages of propylene carbonate in aqueous mixtures. The kinetic parameters of the electrode reaction of Zn(II) and Mn(II), wherever found irreversible, were calculated by Koutecky's treatment³⁻⁴.

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